

ELECTROCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF STEARIC ACID HYDROSOL. PART I.

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For reproducible p_H measurements, coating the platinum electrode with a thin black deposit and then washing with water in a current of hydrogen has been found satisfactory. Electrometric titration of the sols with $Ba(OH)_2$ and $Ca(OH)_2$ show that they should be regarded as a two phase system. The salt formed by the interaction forms a separate phase. The NaOH titration curves resemble to some extent those of weak acid with a strong base. The maximum buffer index, however, does not correspond to half neutralisation but are shifted towards the right corresponding to the addition of larger amounts of alkali. The p_H remains constant between 6.5 and 7.0 in the $Ba(OH)_2$ titrations and between 9 and 9.5 in the NaOH titrations. The total acidity as observed from the inflexion points in the curves agrees fairly with the stoichiometric concentration of the acid. Titration in presence of neutral salts gives the same total acidity as that of the pure sol. Ultrafiltrates of the sol and salt mixtures give only a fraction of the total acidity of the sol.

In a previous paper one of us (S. Mukherjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 17) has shown that the titration curves of palmitic acid hydrosols with different bases give different total acidities and that their properties could be best understood if they were considered to be heterogeneous systems. Kawamura (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, **30**, 1364), while engaged in investigations on the adsorption of $Ba(OH)_2$ and NaOH by solid stearic acid, found that stearates are formed by the interaction and that during the formation the p_H remains constant at 8.0 in the $Ba(OH)_2$ and at 10.0 in the NaOH titrations. In our sols, however, as will be shown later on the p_H remains constant between 6.5 and 7.0 in the $Ba(OH)_2$ and between 9 and 9.5 in the NaOH titration.

Iyer (*Half-yearly J. Mysore Univ.*, 1932, 1) has previously observed different total acidities of stearic acid hydrosols in titrations with NaOH and $Ba(OH)_2$. The form of the titration curves were also found to be different for the two bases. While it appears from the investigations of Iyer (*loc. cit.*) that there is no definite stoichiometric relationship between the amount of alkali used and the acid which reacts with it, S. Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*) using palmitic acid sols observed a definite stoichiometric relationship in titrations with baryta. It was thought desirable to undertake a fuller investigation of stearic acid sols. The results obtained in this work are of some interest in relation to the properties of colloidal acids, *e.g.*

hydrogen clays which also show a difference in the total acidities when titrated with different bases (*Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 1936, 6, 517, 555).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Merck's pure stearic acid and Merck's absolute alcohol were used. The sols were stocked in the same manner as described for palmitic acid sols (S. Mukherjee, *loc. cit.*). The p_H of the sol was mostly measured with the hydrogen electrode against normal calomel electrode (E.M.F. 0.2823 volt at 35°) but the glass electrode and the quinhydrone electrodes were also employed for comparison. A Leeds Northrup K-type potentiometer in conjunction with a Hartmann and Braun galvanometer was used for measuring the potentials. p_H measurements with the glass electrode were carried out with the Morton system of electrodes and an electrometer valve potentiometer obtained from the Cambridge Instrument Company. Before each measurement the glass electrode was checked with two buffer solutions differing by one unit of p_H . To avoid contamination the potentiometric titrations were carried out in a pyrex glass titration cell provided with air-tight ground glass joints. The experimental arrangements in other regards were the same as described in the previous paper. A perforated porcelain bed and 'cella' membranes were employed for ultrafiltration. A water thermostat was used at 35° + 0.05°.

The measurement of the p_H of poorly buffered solutions having low hydrogen ion concentrations is attended with various difficulties. Extreme care is necessary to prevent the access of traces of impurities. The hydrogen electrode is itself often a source of contamination (Kolthoff and Kameda, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 2888). A freshly platinised electrode, which has been washed as usual, often shows a lowering of the p_H as the passage of hydrogen continues, presumably from the liberation of acids adsorbed during platinisation. The use of thinly platinised electrodes with bright deposit recommended by Kolthoff and Kameda (*loc. cit.*) has the disadvantage that the catalytic activity of the electrodes for the reaction, $H^+ + e = H$, dies away within a short time. In previous work in this laboratory erratic variations in the p_H values of such colloidal solutions have often been observed with the hydrogen electrode. On washing and replatinisation its behaviour improved and reproducible values were obtained. Since stearic acid sols have very low hydrogen ion concentrations of the order of $10^{-6}N$, and specific conductivities of the order 10^{-6} mho, the following precautions were taken. Every day, after the measurements,

the platinum deposit on the electrode was removed and the latter was replatinised with a thin dark grey deposit. After washing thoroughly the electrode was kept immersed in conductivity water for about half an hour in a current of hydrogen. They were then again washed with conductivity water and used for the measurements. This procedure proved satisfactory.

The p_H values of stearic acid sols are given in Table I, (g) indicates the glass electrode. Altogether some twelve to sixteen separate p_H determinations were made on each of the sols on different dates, of which only four or five are given below. The rest showed similar variations.

TABLE I.

Sol A		Sol B		Sol C	
Date.	p_H .	Date.	p_H .	Date.	p_H .
5-1-37	5.33	4-2-37	5.45	2-3-37	5.36
14-1-37	5.40	10-2-37	5.39(g)	8-3-37	5.32
25-1-37	5.37	14-2-37	5.32	19-3-37	5.32
		16-2-37	5.33	23-3-37	5.37
29-1-37	5.41	23-2-37	5.36	27-3-37	5.40
4-2-37	5.41	25-2-37	5.39		Mean 5.35
	Mean 5.384		Mean 5.36		

It will be seen that with the precautions taken the reproducibility of the p_H values is fairly satisfactory. The best reproducibility is observed with sols B and C. A cause of the variation perhaps lies in the tendency of the sol to form a deposit of stearic acid on surfaces with which it comes in contact. At the end of the measurement a thin grey coating was observed on the platinum surface and a coating was also noticed on the surface of the glass electrode. The quinhydrone electrode does not give a steady value of the E.M.F. of this sol.

Titration Curves.

The titrations were often repeated to check their reproducibility. The agreement among the replicated curves is satisfactory (see for example curves

FIG. 1.

Sol A.

1 and 2, 5 and 6 for sol A and 7 and 8 for sol B, curves 17 and 18 for sol D). In some cases, however, the agreement is not so close, *e.g.*, curves 9 and 10 for sol B. Irregularities in the kinetics of the interactions appear to be responsible for these discrepancies. The time allowed for the reaction and the rate of stirring have considerable influence on the course of such reactions. This is evident from the titration curve (Fig. 4, curve 19). In this titration increasing amounts of alkali were added to a known volume of the sol in a series of Jena glass bottles. After vigorously shaking the contents, they were kept overnight and the p_H was determined next day. Further complications arise where the sol coagulates, *e.g.*, during titrations with $Ba(OH)_2$ or with neutral salts. Though an attempt has been made to keep the conditions uniform it is not possible to avoid slight variations.

The total acidities have been calculated from the inflexion points with $Ca(OH)_2$ and $Ba(OH)_2$, the inflexion point can be located with an accuracy of about $\pm 2.5\%$ of the total acidity. With $NaOH$, the slope is not so well expressed and the total acidities are liable to larger uncertainties, as much as $\pm 7\%$.

FIG. 2

Sol B.

On gradually adding NH_4OH (Fig. 1, curves 1 and 2) the p_{H} first rises steeply. The slope of the curve decreases but no inflexion point is observed. The reaction is weak till a p_{H} near about 9 is reached when the particles gradually dissolve. NaOH (Fig. 1 curve 3, Fig. 2 curves 7 and 8); resembles NH_4OH to some extent in its interaction but after a flat portion between p_{H} 9.0 and 9.2, the titration curves rise again and show a weak though distinct inflexion near about p_{H} 9.3 resembling that of a weak acid with a strong base.

The p_{H} values at half neutralisation diminishes with an increase in the stearic acid constant (1.77×10^{-6} at 35° , *vide* Part II) and concentration (*vide infra*) similar to that of the stearic acid, the p_{H} at half neutralisation at the following concentrations are given below.

Conc. $\times 10^5 \text{N.}$	p_{H} at half neutralisation.
60	5.77
30	5.78

but the variations observed here are larger than those calculated and the half neutralisation point occurs at a much higher p_{H} .

Other differences are brought out by a calculation of the buffer indices (Van Slyke, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1922, 22, 525). For a weak acid in true solution Van Slyke's expression for the buffer index β is as follows :

$$\beta = \frac{db}{dp_H} = 2.302 \frac{a.k.[H^+]}{k + [H^+]^2} + [H^+] + [OH^-]$$

where b is the amount of base added, a , the initial concentration of the acid. The other symbols have their usual significance.

At the point of half neutralisation β reaches a maximum value, $\beta_{\max} = 0.575a$, which should be independent of the dissociation constant of the acid.

From the NaOH titration curves of sols A and B, the buffer indices have been calculated and plotted against the concentration of the added base in Fig. 1, (curve 3') and Fig. 2 (curves 7' and 8') respectively. The maximum buffer index has unusually large values. The maxima do not correspond exactly to half-neutralisation but are shifted towards the right corresponding to the addition of a larger amount of the alkali. These titration curves thus differ essentially from that of a homogeneous solution of a weak acid.

The titration curves obtained with $Ba(OH)_2$ (Fig. 1, curve 4 ; Fig. 2, curves 9 and 10 ; Fig. 3, curve 11) and $Ca(OH)_2$ (Fig. 1, curves 5 and 6) resembles each other closely. A strong buffering is indicated between p_H 6.5 and 7.0. The form of the curves is similar to those observed by S. Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*) with palmitic acid sols and the same bases. The p_H values at the inflexion points (*vide* Table II) are, however, somewhat higher for the stearic acid sols. Sol D was prepared from stearic acid obtained by twice crystallising Merck's pure stearic acid from absolute alcohol and is considered to be free from certain impurities present in sols A, B, C.

TABLE II.

Sol.	Curve No.	Base used.	p_H in the horizontal part.	p_H at inflexion.
A	4	$Ba(OH)_2$	6.70	7.66
	5	$Ca(OH)_2$	6.47	7.76
	6	"	6.53	7.30
B	9	$Ba(OH)_2$	6.48	7.30
	10	"	6.48	7.50
C	11	$Ba(OH)_2$	6.50	7.75
D	16	$Ba(OH)_2$	6.90	8.50
	17	"	6.95	8.50
	18	"	6.7	8.50

A difference in the titration curves with NaOH and Ba(OH)₂ has been observed by Iyer (*loc. cit.*). With NaOH he obtained a total acidity two-thirds of that with baryta and concluded that an acid sodium stearate, 2NaA.HA and a normal barium salt were formed. The results given below show that in both cases neutral salts are formed.

FIG. 3.

Sol C.

The total acidities obtained from the titration curves and the stoichiometric concentration of stearic acid in the sols, as determined by extraction with ether are given in Table III for comparison.

TABLE III.

Sol.	Base used.	Curve No.	Total acidity by titration.	($N \times 10^5$) by extraction with ether.
A	Ca(OH) ₂	6	59.5	
	NaOH	3	60.0	
B	Ba(OH) ₂	10	41.3*	
	NaOH	7	65.0	
	"	8	65.0	
C	Ba(OH) ₂	11	52.0	53.1
D	Ba(OH) ₂	18	59.0	58.8
	Ba(OH) ₂	16, 17	58.0	
	NaOH	15	58.5	

* This unusually low value is due to inefficient stirring, some of the unreacted stearic acid molecules escaping reaction being enveloped over by insoluble barium stearate formed.

The titration curves can be understood, if one considers the heterogeneous nature of the system. The colloidal particles of stearic acid constitute the solid phase and the intermicellary liquid contains its saturated solution (and perhaps some impurities in traces in the sols A, B, C). When neutralised with $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ or $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$, the Ca or Ba salts of stearic acid, which are insoluble in water, are expected to form a new solid phase. The p_H should at first rise till the solubility product of the salt is reached. Thereafter so long as the two solid phases namely the solid acid and the solid salt co-exist, the p_H should remain unchanged. On the addition of further and sufficient amounts of the base, the solid particles of the acid will disappear and the p_H should again rise sharply and a point of inflexion should mark the neutralisation point. These features are borne out by the titration curves.

FIG. 4.

Sol D.

With NaOH and NH_4OH , the resulting salts are soluble but are hydrolysed. The p_H should sharply rise as happens with a weak acid and a strong alkali. On continued addition of the alkali, the interaction will be weak till a p_H is reached when stearate ions are stable in solution. At and beyond this stage the solid acid dissolves more and more and an inflexion should occur at the equivalence point. On account of the greater hydrolysis of the ammonium salt, the inflexion point of the corresponding

curve is rendered imperceptible. The unneutralised acid is mostly present in the solid form upto the neighbourhood of the equivalence point and the p_H should be higher throughout this portion than what it would be if the same amount of acid were in true solution. The p_H at half neutralisation should therefore vary with concentration and the buffer capacity curve should also have a different form than for a truly dissolved acid.

Neutralisable Acids in presence of Neutral Salts.

S. Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*) found that in presence of barium chloride the whole of the palmitic acid was not neutralised by $Ba(OH)_2$. The incomplete neutralisation was attributed to the inclusion of some of the fatty acid molecules in the coagulum formed by the addition of $BaCl_2$ which did not react with the base under the conditions of the experiment. This was confirmed in the preliminary experiments with stearic acid but it was not thought that it would be possible to ensure true equilibrium. Salt was added inside the cell and the contents were then vigorously stirred and titrated. The results show that the complete equilibrium was attained under these conditions. Sols D and E were made 0.1N in respect of KCl and $BaCl_2$ and then titrated with $Ba(OH)_2$ (Fig. 4, curves 20, 21, 22) and NaOH (Fig. 5, curves 25, 26) respectively. The total acidities calculated from these curves are given below.

FIG. 5.
Sol E.

TABLE IV.

System.	Base used.	Total acidity $\times 10^5 N.$	System.	Base used.	Total acidity $\times 10^5 N.$
Sol D		59.0	Sol D + BaCl ₂	Ba(OH) ₂	58.7
Sol D + KCl	Ba(OH) ₂	60.0	Sol E	NaOH	74.9
Sol D + BaCl ₂	„	59.5	Sol E + KCl	„	73.9
			Sol E + BaCl ₂	„	75.0

The titration of the ultrafiltrate of the sol with Ba(OH)₂ show almost no total acidity (Fig. 3, curve 13). Ultrafiltrate of the sol-KCl mixture shows a total acidity of $5.6 \times 10^{-5} N$ (Fig. 3, curve 12). The ultrafiltrate of the BaCl₂ mixture has the typical properties of a strong acid and has a total acidity of $6.5 \times 10^{-5} N$. (Fig. 3, curve 14; Fig. 5, curve 23).

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